

Potential Antithyroid Agents. Part—V : Synthetic and Pharmacological Studies on Some N-aryl-N'-benzoylthiocarbamides

J. S. UPADHYAYA* and P. K. SRIVASTAVA

Surgical Research Laboratory, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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The thioureylene linkage exhibits certain desired effects required of an antithyroid drug. In search for some specific antithyroid agents, various N-aryl-N'-benzoylthiocarbamides have been synthesised by the condensation of benzoylisothiocyanate with different amines. Preliminary pharmacological investigations of some of the titled compounds showed promising results.

THE antithyroid agents are of great therapeutic interest as they offer a method for correcting a hyperfunctioning gland without resort to surgery. They lower the metabolic rate by interfering with synthesis, release or peripheral action of the thyroid hormone. The highly active antithyroid substances contain thiourea moieties, NHCSNH, capable of being oxidized easily, and suggestion has been made that the interference with thyroxine synthesis is by a direct reaction between I_2 and SH (formed by enolization) to form a disulphide¹⁻⁴. As a part of general study directed towards the development of antithyroid agents⁵⁻⁹, the above rationale led to a study of synthesis and biological evaluation of N-aryl-N'-benzoylthiocarbamides.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and pharmacological studies of some N-aryl-N'-benzoylthiocarbamides. The interest in the studies of these compounds as antithyroid drugs is due to the fact that acylisothiocyanates possess enhanced reactivity on account of the electron withdrawing acyl groups attached to the thioureido linkage and the acylisothiocyanates, on reaction with amino compounds, usually give acyl derivatives of thiocarbamides. The synthesis has been effected by the condensation of benzoylisothiocyanate with different amines.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets and a Perkin-Elmer 720 infracord spectrophotometer; bands reported were at least of medium intensity. The results of elemental analyses were in good agreement with those of theoretical values.

Benzoylisothiocyanate: It was prepared by the method reported in literature⁹.

N-(p-Tolyl)-N'-benzoylthiocarbamide¹⁰: A warm solution of benzoylisothiocyanate (8.15 g; 0.05

mole) in acetone (50 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of *p*-toluidine (5.35 g; 0.05 mole) in acetone (50 ml) over a period of about 10 min. An exothermic reaction took place and the reaction mixture deposited a pale yellow crystalline product which was collected, washed with water and dried. It gave colourless shining needles from 70% ethanol, yield 13.58 g (97%); m.p. 157°. Anal. Found: N, 10.28; S, 11.74. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{14}N_2OS$; N, 10.37; S, 11.85%.

Similarly, other N-aryl-N'-benzoylthiocarbamides were prepared by the condensation of benzoylisothiocyanate with different amines. The purification was achieved by several times recrystallisation with 70% ethanol (Table 1).

N-Aryl-N'-benzoylthiocarbamides have been characterised by elemental analyses; ir spectra: 1510 (N=C=S), 1620 (C=N), 1300 (NH), 1680 (C=O) and 780 cm^{-1} (substituted benzene ring).

Pharmacological screening¹¹⁻¹⁵: Male Sprague-Dawley rats (100-125 g) were maintained on a low-iodide diet for 3 days, then divided into groups of 4 rats each. Each animal in all the groups received an intraperitoneal injection of 1 ml of physiological saline, thiouracil, or one of the test compounds followed by, 1 μ Cu of $Na^{131}I$ after 1 hr. The animals were sacrificed and the thyroids removed. The whole lobes were placed in ground glass homogenizing tubes and counted in a Nuclear-Chicago well scintillation counter to determine total thyroid uptake. The whole lobes were then homogenized in 1 ml of 0.05 M barbital buffer (pH 8.6) containing 1.0×10^{-6} M thiouracil. 1 ml of cold 20% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added and the homogenate was centrifuged. The precipitate was washed twice with 1.0 ml of cold 10% TCA. The original supernatant liquid and the two washings were combined and the radioactivity determined. The ^{131}I in this fraction indicated the concentration of inorganic ^{131}I or TCA soluble ^{131}I . The washed precipitate was counted in the

* Corresponding address: Institute of Paper Technology, (University of Roorkee), Saharanpur-247 001.

TABLE 1—N-ARYL-N'-BENZOYLTHIOCARBAMIDES

No.	R	Yield, %	Melting point °C
1.	H	90	140
2.	2-CH ₃	95	117
3.	3-CH ₃	85	121
4.	4-CH ₃ *	97	157
5.	2-OCH ₃	88	123
6.	3-OCH ₃	84	107
7.	4-OCH ₃ *	86	147
8.	2-Cl*	91	120
9.	3-Cl	85	125
10.	4-Cl	90	136
11.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	86	119
12.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	92	152
13.	4-Br	82	160
14.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	85	150
15.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	89	98
16.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	87	127
17.	2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	80	142
18.	2,5-(OCH ₃) ₂	86	138
19.	2,5-(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂	81	152
20.	2,3-Cl ₂	78	156
21.	2,4-Cl ₂	76	147
22.	2,5-Cl ₂	79	150

* Known compounds.

All the compounds gave consistent N and S analyses.

TABLE 2—PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF N-ARYL-N'-BENZOYLTHIOCARBAMIDES AS ANTITHYROID AGENTS IN INTACT RATS

Compounds	Thyroid radioactivity, dpm ± std error			Approximate estimated activity (thiouracil = 1.0)
	¹²⁵ I uptake	PB ¹²⁵ I	Inorganic ¹²⁵ I	
Blank	8478 ± 50	7196 ± 14	1238 ± 28	1.0
Thiouracil	4463 ± 62	3822 ± 30	620 ± 18	<1
1.	5342 ± 25	4698 ± 15	624 ± 12	<1
2.	5484 ± 13	4837 ± 13	609 ± 16	<1
3.	5650 ± 16	5112 ± 14	510 ± 20	<1
4.	5722 ± 14	5121 ± 13	581 ± 16	<1
5.	4920 ± 17	4226 ± 14	658 ± 25	<1
6.	4822 ± 13	4014 ± 16	648 ± 17	<1
7.	4882 ± 15	4160 ± 18	647 ± 12	<1
8.	4626 ± 12	4025 ± 16	542 ± 18	<1
9.	4768 ± 16	4176 ± 10	567 ± 13	>1
10.	4294 ± 18	3712 ± 17	530 ± 15	<1
11.	5468 ± 14	4718 ± 12	678 ± 16	<1
12.	5371 ± 20	4781 ± 22	559 ± 13	<1
13.	5016 ± 12	4528 ± 20	448 ± 17	<1
14.	5520 ± 18	4892 ± 20	582 ± 14	<1
15.	5730 ± 15	5124 ± 12	572 ± 13	<1
16.	5650 ± 18	5127 ± 18	508 ± 16	<1
17.	5621 ± 12	4973 ± 20	613 ± 14	<1
18.	4632 ± 22	4008 ± 13	608 ± 14	<1
19.	4649 ± 15	4124 ± 12	503 ± 12	>1
20.	4038 ± 22	3489 ± 12	526 ± 14	>1
21.	4175 ± 19	3562 ± 18	582 ± 18	>1
22.	4382 ± 24	3698 ± 15	675 ± 11	>1

homogenizing tube. The radioactivity in this fraction indicated the PB¹²⁵I (protein-bound-iodine) or the TCA precipitable¹²⁵I. The counts were all corrected for counting efficiency and expressed as disintegration per minute.

All the compounds were dissolved in physiological saline for injection. Thiouracil was dissolved with heating to 55°. Some of the compounds were injected as a suspension in saline. All compounds were assayed at concentrations equimolar to thiouracil. Table 2 summarizes the results of screening of these compounds.

All compounds possess antithyroid activity to some extent and appear to inhibit incorporation of I₂ in a manner similar to thiouracil. Compounds No. 10, 20, 21 and 22 appear to be slightly more potent than thiouracil.

Mode of action and effect of substituents on anti-thyroid activity: The thioureyline linkage in these compounds is capable of forming an-SH grouping by enolisation. The suggestion has been made that the interference with thyroxine synthesis was by a direct reaction between iodine and sulphhydryl groupings to form a disulphide¹⁶. Since this reaction proceeds at a rate considerably faster than the iodination of tyrosyl group, the competition could be quite favourable for diversion of iodine away from organic binding.

These data suggest that a disulphide bond in thyroid tissue is cleaved by antithyroid compounds containing a thioureyline linkage to form a new disulphide bond. This formulation is supported

by chemical studies in which thiourea was found to cleave the disulphide bond of cystine to yield the mixed disulphide s-guanylthio-l-cysteine¹⁷.

It is evident from the results of pharmacological studies that the introduction of chloro group in a benzene ring enhances the activity upto some extent.

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